

Rubeanic Acid and its Derivatives as Chelating Ligands and Analytical Reagents

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Rubeanic acid or dithio-oxamide, although its lead salt was first described by Wöhler¹ in the early 1825, remained, however, practically in the dark, relating to its reaction with metallic ions, till a century later Rây and Ray² in 1926 revealed its usefulness and potentiality as a reagent for the detection of traces of cobalt, nickel, and copper with which it was found to form intensely and characteristically coloured complexes³. Since then the reagent has received considerable attention from various workers, particularly within the last few years, for use as a chelating ligand in colorimetric analysis and spot reactions of metals. Not only the parent compound, but many of its substituted derivatives have also been investigated for the purpose with a view to improving the selectivity of the reagent and the solubility of the coloured complexes formed. The structure of the metal chelates has also been under close examination and evidences have been recorded about the possibility of their forming long-chain polymeric molecules. But the analytical application of the reagent and many of its derivatives for spectrophotometric determination of a number of transition metals has received by far the wider attention and interest.

In recent years rubeanic acid and its derivatives, as well as their metal complexes, are being investigated for application in many other fields, and suggestions have already been made for their uses as metal deactivators, pigments, accelerators in vulcanization, ingredients for duplicating processes, herbicides, rodent repellents, organic intermediates, etc.

With a view to stimulating further interest in this interesting series of compounds with possibilities for application in diverse fields of pure and applied chemistry, it appears to be the right time for an attempt to collect and assess all pertinent information relating to the study of rubeanic acid and its derivatives and of their metal complexes in the form of a short review.

Furthermore, we feel that the right place for its publication will be in the Acharya Prafulla Chandra Rây Birth-Centenary Celebration Number of the Journal of the Indian Chemical Society, as the late Acharya Rây was greatly interested in the study of co-ordination complexes of many allied organic thio-compounds, particularly of the mercaptans and thioethers, with platinum metals.

Preparation

Rubeanic acid is prepared by passing dry cyanogen gas into an alcoholic solution of KSH (alcoholic KOH saturated with H₂S) in the cold. The solution is thereafter acidified

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with hydrochloric acid, when rubeanic acid is precipitated in the form of a red-brown product. This is then purified by recrystallization from 95% alcohol, using animal charcoal.⁴⁻⁷

In another method described in the literature^{9,9}, a concentrated solution of copper sulphate in aqueous ammonia is treated with potassium cyanide in the cold. The solution is filtered from any insoluble residue and saturated with H_2S . On cooling, the crystals of rubeanic acid separate. The yield is rather poor and the method is seldom used.

The reaction leading to the formation of rubeanic acid consists in the mere addition of hydrogen sulphide to cyanogen molecule. It may therefore be viewed as sulph-hydrolysis of cyanogen to form dithio-oxamide corresponding to the formation of oxamide from cyanogen by hydrolysis:

Alkyl-substituted rubeanic acids are obtained by warming rubeanic acid with the corresponding amine in aqueous or alcoholic solution¹⁰⁻¹⁴.

In this manner *NN'*-dialkyldithio-oxamides containing straight-chain alkyl derivatives from dimethyl to dioctadecyl as well as diallyl dithio-oxamides have been prepared. Branch chain derivatives like diisopropyl, diisobutyl and dicyclohexylrubeanic acids have likewise been obtained¹⁴. Condensation of rubeanic acid with amines bearing other substituents, namely, ethanolamine, benzylamine, 3-dimethylaminopropylamine, 2-acetoxyethylamine and the sodium salts of aminoacetic acid and 2-aminoethylsulphonic acid (taurine), has led to the preparation of *NN'*-dibenzyl, *NN'*-bis-2-acetoxyethyl, 2-hydroxyethyl, 3-dimethylaminopropyl, carboxyethyl, and sulphyoxyethyl dithio-oxamides¹⁴. *NN'*-Diphenylrubeanic acid was obtained along with the monothio-oxamide, $C_6H_5NHSCCONHC_6H_5$, by the action of phosphorus pentasulphide on oxanilide in boiling xylene. The dithio compound is separated from the monothio derivative by dissolving the product in dilute (5%) sodium hydroxide solution, followed by reprecipitation with carbon dioxide. The process is repeated several times. The final products are recrystallized from glacial acetic acid¹⁵.

Properties

(1) *Physical*.—Table I records the appearance, melting point, and solubility of rubeanic acid and some of its derivatives. Solubility values are all quoted from Mallinckrodt Chemical Works Publication¹⁴.

TABLE I

Reagent.	Appearance.	M.P.	Solubility (25°) (g./100 c.c.).
Rubeanic acid (Rba) $CSNH_2$ $CSNH_2$	Orange-red crystals	Decomp. at 140° without melting	Water (0.04), ethanol (0.56), methanol (1.0), acetone (3.2), chloroform (3.0), benzene (1.3), carbon disulphide (0.2), carbon tetrachloride (0.10), ethyl acetate (1.4)

TABLE I (contd.)

Reagent.	Appearance.	M.P.	Solubility (25°) (g./100 c.c.).
<i>NN'</i> -Dimethyl Rba CSNHCH ₃ CSNHCH ₃	Yellow crystals	140° (138°)	Water (0.13), ethanol (1.5), methanol (2.0), acetone (11.5), chloroform (14.9), benzene (6.6), carbon disulphide (3.5), carbon tetrachloride (3.8), ethyl acetate (6.6).
<i>NN'</i> -Diethyl Rba CSNHC ₂ H ₅ CSNHC ₂ H ₅	Yellowish red cryst.	58°	Resembles the dimethyl derivative in solubility; data wanting.
<i>NN'</i> -Diisoamyl Rba CSNHC ₃ H ₁₁ CSNHC ₃ H ₁₁	Orange prismatic cryst.	59-60°	Do
<i>NN'</i> -bis-(2-hydroxy-ethyl) Rba. CSNHCH ₂ CH ₂ OH CSNHCH ₂ CH ₂ OH	Orange-yellow cryst.	93-94°	Water (1.0), ethanol (10.4), methanol (18.4), acetone (19.0), chloroform (0.32), benzene (0.18), carbon disulphide (0.10), carbon tetrachloride (0.10), ethyl acetate (3.5).
<i>NN'</i> -Dibenzyl Rba CSNHCH ₂ C ₆ H ₅ CSNHCH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	Yellowish red cryst.	115° (110°)	Water (0.14), ethanol (0.25), methanol (0.25), acetone (4.9), chloroform (15.9), benzene (5.2), carbon disulphide (6.5), carbon tetrachloride (2.4), ethyl acetate (4.0).
<i>NN'</i> -bis-(carboxy-methyl) Rba. CSNHCH ₂ COOH CSNHCH ₂ COOH	Light brown powder	208.6°- 210° (decomp.)	Water (0.77), ethanol (2.5), methanol (6.4), acetone (2.8), chloroform (0.18), benzene (0.20), carbon disulphide (0.22), carbon tetrachloride (0.18), ethyl acetate (0.85).
<i>NN'</i> -Dicyclohexyl Rba CSNHC ₆ H ₁₁ CSNHC ₆ H ₁₁	Bright orange-red powder	146.3- 148°	Water (0.12), ethanol (0.40), methanol (0.34), acetone (1.2), chloroform (24.4), benzene (8.5), carbon disulphide (18.8), carbon tetrachloride (13.8), ethyl acetate (1.70).
<i>NN'</i> -Didodecyl Rba CSNHC ₁₂ H ₂₅ CSNHC ₁₂ H ₂₅	Straw-coloured powder	49.8°- 51.8°	Water (0.06), ethanol (2.0), methanol (2.0), acetone (8.0), chloroform (53.0), benzene (43.5), carbon disulphide (57.0), carbon tetrachloride (46.0), ethyl acetate (13.0).
<i>NN'</i> -Diphenyl Rba CSNHC ₆ H ₅ CSNHC ₆ H ₅	Shining orange-red plates	133° 134°	Resembles the dibenzyl derivative in solubility; data wanting.

The acidity constant, solubility product, and solubility of rubeanic acid were determined by potentiometric method⁶ with the results: K_a (acid dissociation constant) =

$(1.28 \pm 0.04) \times 10^{-21}$; K_{sp} (solubility product) $= 3.9 \pm 0.12 \times 10^{-14}$; and S (solubility) $= (3.07 \pm 0.04) \times 10^{-3}$ mole per litre.

A consideration of the solubility data for rubeanic acid and its derivatives as given in Table I seems to suggest that although a polar substituent in the molecule more or less increases the solubility of the derivative in polar solvents and reduces its solubility in non-polar solvents, a non-polar substituent in the molecule, on the other hand, acts in the reverse way. This is rather a very rough approximation as several other factors are known to influence the phenomenon of solubility. Water being highly associated behaves somewhat anomalously in this respect.

Bradley and Cleasby¹⁷ have studied the vapour pressure of rubeanic acid over a limited range of temperature (86.9-104.15°) and have determined its lattice energy and entropy of vaporization. The values obtained for the two latter are comparable to those of oxamide; the lattice energy value is, however, lower but the entropy value is slightly higher.

	Lattice Energy (cal./mole)		Entropy of vaporization (cal/degree/mole)	
Oxamide	..	27,300	..	44.4
Rubeanic acid	..	25,200	..	45.0

The crystal structure of rubeanic acid has been studied by means of X-ray diffraction by Long *et al.*¹⁸

The infrared spectra of rubeanic acid as also of its derivatives have been studied^{14,19}. Rubeanic acid shows three strong bands at 3304, 3205, and 3135 cm^{-1} , and the spectrum resembles that of *N*-methylacetamide. The infrared spectra of rubeanic acid and its derivatives indicate that in the crystalline state they exist predominantly in the keto form.

(b) *Chemical Properties.*—Rubeanic acid and its derivatives are very weak acids, soluble in dilute aqueous alkalis, and can be reprecipitated from the solution by acidification^{10,11}. It might be noted here that the present authors have found that some of the substituted rubeanic acids like *NN'*-dimethyl-, -diethyl- and -diphenylrubeanic acids form colorless solution in caustic alkalis, but others like *NN'*-diisoamyl- and *NN'*-bis-(2-hydroxyethyl) rubeanic acids retain their colour unchanged in dilute alkali solution. Rubeanic acid itself also shows its usual colour in dilute aqueous alkalis. This suggests some unstable structural change predominating in the case of dimethyl, diethyl and diphenyl derivatives. It is likely to have some connection with the formation of aci- or semiaci- form of the substance (*vide infra*). In boiling concentrated caustic alkali solution rubeanic acid is decomposed with the formation of alkali sulphide, alkali cyanide, and alkali thiocyanate. When a solution in dilute aqueous alkali is boiled, it decomposes giving rise to alkali sulphide and alkali oxalate with liberation of ammonia³. In boiling dilute hydrochloric acid rubeanic acid suffers hydrolysis with formation of ammonium chloride, oxalic acid and hydrogen sulphide. Similar decomposition in hot alkalis and acids has also been reported for the *NN'*-disubstituted derivatives of rubeanic acid.

It has been observed by polarographic study that dithic-oxamide (rubeanic acid) in acid, basic, or neutral solution suffers reduction in two steps²⁰.

Rubeanic acid has been found to undergo condensation with mixtures of aldehydes and secondary amines²¹. It also suffers cyclization with α -halogen carbonyl compounds²²⁻²³.

Rubeanic acid reacts with hydrazine to form the dihydrazone of oxamide with liberation of H_2S ²⁶ and with hydroxylamine to yield oxalamidoxime¹⁴.

TABLE II

Characteristic properties of metal rubeanates

Rubeanic acid = Rba. *NN'*-disubstituted derivatives: Dimethyl-, diethyl-bis-(2-hydroxyethyl)-, diisooamyl-, dibenzyl-, and diphenyl rubeanic acid = Me₂Rba, Et₂Rba, (hydroxy-Et)₂Rba, (iso-Am)₂Rba, Bz₂Rba, and Ph₂Rba respectively.

Metal	Rba (1)	Me ₂ Rba(2)	Et ₂ Rba(3)	(Hydroxy-Et) ₂ Rba(4)	(iso-Am) ₂ Rba (5)	Bz ₂ Rba (6)	Ph ₂ Rba (7)
Ag(I)	Yellow ppt., somewhat soluble in water	Orange-yellow ppt., decomposed by dil. acids and alkalis	Same as (2)	Yellow ppt., soluble in excess of alcohol	Same as (4)	Pale yellow ppt.	Yellow ppt., slightly soluble in organic solvents
Hg(I&II)	White ppt.	Same as (1)	Same as (1)	Same as (1)	Same as (1)		
Bi(III)	Yellowish brown ppt.						Yellow to brown ppt.
Pb(II)	Yellow ppt.	Same as (1)	Same as (1)	Same as (1)	Same as (1)	Yellowish white ppt.	Same as (1)
Cu(II)	Greenish black ppt., very sparingly soluble in pyridine, in butyl alcohol, ethyl or amyl acetate	Deep green ppt. with a blue tinge	Same as (2)	Dark green ppt. with a violet tinge, very sparingly soluble in benzene or toluene, soluble in pyridine with a greenish yellow colour extractable by amyl alcohol	Dark green ppt. with a blue tinge, soluble in pyridine with a greenish yellow colour	Dark green ppt. with a blue tinge, soluble in pyridine with a greenish yellow colour	Soluble in pyridine with a greenish yellow colour extractable by amyl alcohol
Ca(II)	Yellow ppt.						Pale yellow ppt.
Fe(II)	Blue ppt.						
Zn(II)	White ppt.						

TABLE II (cont'd.)

Metal	Rba(1)	Me ₃ Rba(2)	Et ₂ Rba(3)	(Hydroxy-Et) ₂ Rba(4)	(iso-Am) ₃ Rba(5)	Hz ₂ Rba(6)	Ph ₃ Rba(7)
Co(II)	Brown ppt., soluble in pyridine, giving orange-yellow soln. slightly soluble in amyl and butyl alcohol, acetone, ethyl and amyl acetate and in triethanolamine	Same as(1); colour of pyridine solution extractable by amyl or butyl alcohol, acetate and chloroform	Same as(2); colour of the pyridine soln. also extractable by benzene and toluene	Brownish yellow ppt., soluble in pyridine to give an orange-yellow soln. colour extractable by butyl or amyl alcohol, ethyl or amyl acetate	Dark brown ppt. fairly soluble in benzene, toluene, CHCl ₃ , CCl ₄ , amyl or butyl alcohol, ethyl or amyl acetate; soluble in pyridine with an orange-yellow colour extractable by toluene, chloroform, etc.; soluble in pyridine with an orange-yellow colour extractable by butyl or amyl alcohol	Deep brown ppt., soluble in pyridine with an orange-yellow colour extractable by toluene, chloroform, etc.; soluble in pyridine with an orange-yellow colour extractable by butyl or amyl alcohol	Orange-brown ppt., sparingly soluble in acetone; easily soluble in benzene, toluene, chloroform, etc.; soluble in pyridine with an orange-yellow colour extractable by butyl or amyl alcohol
Ni(II)	Blue-violet ppt., dissolves in pyridine to a pink soln.	Red-violet ppt., otherwise same as (1); pyridine colour extractable by common solvents.	Purple-red ppt., otherwise same as (2)	Deep violet ppt., otherwise same as (2)	Same as(4); pyridine colour extractable by butyl or amyl alcohol, acetate	Deep violet ppt., fairly soluble in acetone, benzene, CHCl ₃ , butyl or amyl alcohol, ethyl or amyl acetate; easily soluble in pyridine with a reddish pink colour deep violet colour extractable by butyl or amyl alcohol	Deep violet ppt., sparingly soluble in acetone, ethanol, amyl alcohol, ethyl or amyl acetate; easily soluble in pyridine with a reddish pink colour extractable by butyl or amyl alcohol

TABLE II (contd.)

Metal	Rba(1)	Me _n Rba(2)	Et ₂ Rba (3)	(Hydroxy·Et) ₂ Rba(4)	(iso-Am) ₂ Rba (5)	Hz ₂ Rba (6)	Ph ₂ Rba (7)
Pd(II)	Red ppt., soluble in pyridine to give an orange-yellow soln., colour extractable by amyl alcohol; soluble in acetone, tri-ethanolamine, amyl and butyl alcohol, ethyl and amyl acetate	Orange-yellow ppt., otherwise same as(1)	Same as (2)	Orange-red fairly soluble in ethanol, butyl and amyl alcohol, acetone; easily soluble in pyridine; pyridine colour extractable by amyl or butyl alcohol, ethyl or amyl acetate and CHCl ₃	Deep red ppt., soluble in almost all common organic solvents; yellow colour of the pyridine soln. extractable by butyl or amyl alcohol	Orange-yellow ppt., soluble in acetone, chloroform, ethyl or amyl acetate and pyridine; yellow colour of pyridine soln. is extractable by butyl or amyl alcohol, toluene, benzene, etc. The solution in these solvents is rather unstable	Deep red ppt., soluble in most of the common organic solvents; the orange-yellow colour of the pyridine soln. is extractable by butyl or amyl alcohol, CHCl ₃ , CCl ₄ and ethyl or amyl acetate
Au(III)	Orange ppt.	Yellow ppt.	Orange-yellow ppt.	Orange-yellow soln. giving a brown ppt. on standing	Golden yellow colour	Pale yellow ppt.	Orange-red ppt.
Ru (III & IV)	Blue ppt. giving a blue solution in strong acids	Same as (1)	Same as (1)	Same as (1)	Blue solution readily giving a blue ppt.		Greenish blue coloration, readily giving a ppt.
Pt(IV)	Rose-red	Yellow ppt.	Orange-brown ppt.	Orange-yellow soln. giving a brown ppt. on standing	Yellow ppt.	Orange-yellow coloration	Brownish red unstable ppt.
Tl(I)	Yellow ppt.						

With benzaldehyde rubeanic acid reacts to produce a thiazolo-thiazole derivative^{27,28}.

With many metal ions in solution rubeanic acid and its derivatives react to form intensely coloured insoluble precipitates^{2,14,29-37}.

Almost all metal ions, which give precipitates with sulphide ion in acid, neutral, or alkaline solution, are precipitated by rubeanic acid and its derivatives* (disubstituted). The colour and properties of these metal compounds of rubeanic acid and some of its derivatives, are recorded in Table II, mainly from the observation of Rây and Ray and of Xavier and Rây³⁷.

The solubility values of copper (II), nickel (II) and cobalt (II) rubeanates in neutral, alkaline, and acid solutions, as determined by Malyuga³⁸ along with the values of their solubility products in water given by the same author, are quoted in Table IIA.

TABLE IIA

Metal	Solubility product	Solubility (in moles per litre) at 18° in			
		Water	0.01M aq. NH ₃	Soln. containing 0.1M-NH ₄ Cl, 0.010M, NaOH & 0.1M citric acid	0.001M HCl
Copper	7.67×10^{-16}	5.8×10^{-8}	7.7×10^{-7}	6.8×10^{-8}	3.0×10^{-7}
Nickel	1.1×10^{-15}	7.2×10^{-8}	7.6×10^{-7}	7.5×10^{-8}	1.1×10^{-6}
Cobalt	1.2×10^{-15}	7.4×10^{-8}	9.0×10^{-7}	5.4×10^{-8}	6.7×10^{-7}

Compounds of rubeanic acid with Fe(II), Au(III), Pt(IV), Hg(I & II), Bi(III), Pb(II), Cd(II) and Tl(I) are all unstable, decomposing more or less into the corresponding sulphide. Copper, nickel and cobalt are precipitated quantitatively from slightly acid or ammoniacal solution; silver and thallium from neutral solution; iron, lead and cadmium from neutral or alkaline solution; mercury, bismuth, palladium, gold, platinum and ruthenium from acid solution. In an excess of mineral acids ruthenium gives a blue solution.

A consideration of the properties of metal rubeanates, as recorded in Table II, shows that *NN'*-disubstituted derivatives of rubeanic acid differ but little in their reaction with metal ions from their parent body (rubeanic acid), except in a gradual change in the colour shade and solubility of the product with the nature and size of the substituent. On the other hand, it has been found that a tetra-substituted derivative, tetraethylrubeanic acid, fails to give any characteristic reaction with metal ions^{32,39}, due obviously to the absence of any hydrogen atom available for salt formation.

Structure

Rubeanic acid is identified with dithio-oxamide as it results from the sulphhydrolysis of cyanogen, in analogy with the formation of oxamide from cyanogen by hydrolysis. In solution it is likely to occur therefore as an equilibrium mixture of the tautomeric thione (I), thione-thiol (II) and thiol (III) forms, denominated otherwise as diamido or base, amid-imido or semi-aci, and diimido or aci forms respectively.

In addition, a dissociation equilibrium for II and III, however small, must also be taken into account, which is responsible for its salt-forming or acid character. Moreover, all these forms may again occur in their corresponding isomeric *trans* or *anti*-configuration. Each of these forms of the *cis* or *trans* type may further resonate among several valence bond structures on account of conjugation in the molecule^{9,10}.

The X-ray diffraction study of single crystals of rubeanic acid by Long *et al.*¹⁰ shows that each unit cell contains two planar molecules, each lying on a centre of symmetry and that C-C bond length corresponds to that for a single bond, while C-N and C-S distances partake of double bond character. The results are indicative of a *trans* configuration of the molecule resonating among the structures like:

In solution, when the crystal structure is destroyed, the molecule may, however, assume partially a *cis* configuration as well, besides tautomerising into thione-thiol and thiol forms.

On the basis of his study of the infrared absorption spectra of rubeanic acid Barcelo¹⁰ has assigned a chain-like polymeric formula IV for the compound, representing it as a body of associated molecules.

The structure suggested is based primarily on a comparison of the N-H stretching frequencies of the rubeanic acid with those of *N*-methylacetamide in the region of 3,000-3,400 cm^{-1} . No direct evidence from the spectra of rubeanic acid itself may be said to have been furnished. Moreover, the X-ray spectra of rubeanic acid provide no indication of such a chain-like polymeric structure for the substance (cf. Long *et al.*)¹⁰.

No evidence has yet been reported, however, about the association of rubeanic acid molecules in solution in any solvent.

Metal Rubeanates

(a) *Preparation and Properties*—Copper (II), nickel (II) and cobalt (II) rubeanates were described by Ray and Ray².

When an alcoholic solution of rubeanic acid is added to a slight excess of copper sulphate solution, copper rubeanate is precipitated as a voluminous slimy greenish black

mass, which after washing and drying changes to black shining scales. The composition, based on the analysis of the dry product, corresponds more closely with $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_2\text{S}_2\text{N}_2\text{H}_2) \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ than with the anhydrous body. When heated above 160° the compound decomposes. It dissolves with decomposition in moderately strong boiling hydrochloric acid, and is decomposed by boiling caustic alkali with formation of copper sulphide, alkali cyanide and sulphocyanide.

Nickel rubeanate is obtained as a bluish violet slimy precipitate in a similar manner from an aqueous solution of nickel salt: but no precipitation occurs unless the solution is rendered alkaline with sodium acetate or dilute ammonia. In presence of strong ammonia an intense red product separates, changing readily into the bluish violet compound. The compound shows the composition $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{S}_2\text{N}_2\text{H}_2)$. It resembles the copper rubeanate in properties, but dissolves partially in 8% ammonia to form a bluish violet solution and forms a deep orange-red solution in stronger ammonia. In caustic alkali it dissolves to a yellowish red solution, which turns pink when diluted. From this solution the bluish violet nickel rubeanate is reprecipitated by neutralization.

Nickel (II) compounds of some substituted rubeanic acids, viz., *NN'*-dimethyl (I), -dibenzyl (II), -dioctadecyl (III), -bis-(2-hydroxyethyl) (IV), -bis-(2-acetoxyethyl) (V), and -bis-(3-dimethylaminopropyl) rubeanic acid, have been recently described by Hurd *et al.*²² They can be represented by the general formula: $[\text{Ni}(\text{RNSCCSNR})]_n$, where $\text{R} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2$, $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{37}$, $\text{HOH}_2\text{CCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_2$ and $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{NCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2$.

With dimethylrubeanic acid nickel, however, showed variable composition depending on the manner of its preparation and purification. When prepared in the absence of any base in aqueous alcoholic solution, the composition of the product obtained is represented by the authors as (DMR) $[(\text{Ni}(\text{DMR}\cdot 2\text{H}))_4 \text{Ni}(\text{DMR})]$; where $\text{DMR} = \text{CH}_3\text{HNSCCSNHCH}_3$ and $\text{DMR} - 2\text{H} = \text{CH}_3\text{NSCCSNCH}_3$. When prepared in the presence of an alkali the products contained sodium in addition. These have been represented by the composition: $[(\text{DMR}\cdot 2\text{H})\text{Ni}]_{6.8} (\text{DMR}\cdot \text{H})\text{Na}$ and $\text{Na}[(\text{DMR}\cdot 2\text{H})\text{Ni}]_{1.8} (\text{DMR}\cdot \text{H})\text{Na}$. All these compounds were regarded as more or less highly polymerised, the value of n being quite high.

With ammonia, methylamine, triisopropanolamine, di-(aminopropyl)amine, ethylenediamine and *o*-phenanthroline, nickel(II) rubeanate and Ni(II) *NN'*-dimethylrubeanate are reported to form insoluble products of intense purple, blood-red, dark red or red-brown colour²⁴.

All the nickel (II) rubeanates that have been described are highly coloured solids of various shades of blue, violet and purple. The nickel(II) dimethylrubeanate is crystalline and paramagnetic (B.M. = 2.4.).

Cobalt rubeanate is obtained as a reddish brown hygroscopic powder from a cobalt salt solution and rubeanic acid in presence of sodium acetate or ammonia. It has the composition $\text{Co}(\text{C}_2\text{S}_2\text{N}_2\text{H}_2) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and resembles the nickel rubeanate in properties.

By the action of an aqueous alcoholic solution of rubeanic acid on an ammoniacal solution of carbonatotetramminecobaltic nitrate a dull brown insoluble cobalt (III) rubeanate of the composition, $\text{Co}_2(\text{C}_2\text{S}_2\text{N}_2\text{H}_2)_3 (\text{NH}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, has been obtained; this on drying at $115^\circ - 120^\circ$ loses $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The occurrence of cobalt (III) rubeanate as $\text{Co}_2(\text{C}_2\text{N}_2\text{H}_2)_3$ in solution at pH 9 in presence of a protective colloid like gum acacia, which serves to keep the compound in solution, has been demonstrated by Jacobs and Yoe²⁵ by spectrophotometric measurements following three independent methods: the mole ratio method of Yoe and Jones²⁶, continuous variation method of Job as modified by Vosburg and Cooper²⁷, and the slope

ratio method of Harvey and Manning⁴³. It appears therefore that in alkaline solution cobalt (II) rubeanate is oxidized to the cobalt (III) compound. Alike spectrophotometric measurements on copper (II) and nickel (II) rubeanates in solution containing gum acacia have confirmed their empirical composition with 1 mole ion of copper or nickel for 1 mole of the reagent⁴⁰. These observations have also been confirmed by the same authors⁴⁴ using a derivative of rubeanic acid as well, namely, *NN''*-bis-(3-dimethylaminopropyl) rubeanic acid. The same conclusion regarding the composition of copper rubeanate was arrived at previously from physico-chemical studies of the copper rubeanic acid system by Tananaev and Levitman⁴⁵.

Palladium has been found to combine with rubeanic acid to afford a number of compounds having the composition Pd_3Rba_2 , PdRba , Pd_2Rba_3 and PdRba_3 (where Rba = a rubeanic acid molecule or its radical), depending on the *pH* value of the medium during precipitation and the amount of the reagent present. Compositions of these compounds were determined both by heterometric titration of palladium chloride solution with rubeanic acid as well as by microanalysis of the dried products⁴⁶. A compound of the composition, $\text{Pd}(\text{C}_2\text{S}_2\text{N}_2\text{H}_2)_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_2\text{S}_2\text{N}_2\text{H}_4$, also was described by Wolbling and Steiger³². In this the reagent is supposed to react in its semi-aci form.

Spectrophotometric measurement of the optical density of the blue coloured solutions derived from ruthenium salts and rubeanic acid has shown that both Ru (III) and Ru (IV) form the same complexes. $[\text{RuSC}(\text{NH})\text{CSNH}_2]^{2+}$ and $\text{Ru}[\text{SC}(\text{NH})\text{CSNH}_2]_3$; in these the reagent seems to react in its semi-aci form⁴⁷. The formation constants of the compounds have also been determined by these authors.

The formation of gold rubeanates of composition, Au_3Rba_2 , AuRba and AuRba_3 , analogous to those of palladium, has also been established by Bobtelsky and Eisentadter⁴⁶ by heterometric titration and analysis as with palladium. A gold compound of the composition, $[\text{Au}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2]_2 \cdot \text{C}_2\text{S}_2\text{N}_2\text{H}_2$, has also been described⁴⁸.

(b) *Structure*.—Rây and Ray were the first to suggest that rubeanic acid reacts with metal ions in its aci or dithiol form, giving rise to inner metal complexes, as it can then offer both salt-forming (-SH) and coordinating (=NH) groups. The structure V with two interpenetrating 5-membered rings was proposed by them for the rubeanates of copper (II), nickel (II) and cobalt (II).

where $\text{M} = \text{Cu}(\text{II}), \text{Ni}(\text{II})$ or $\text{Co}(\text{II})$.

As the nickel complex was found to be diamagnetic⁴⁹ it must be assumed that the metal atom should be linked to the sulphur and nitrogen atoms in a square planar configuration⁵⁰. But this is likely to involve a considerable strain in the molecule, rendering it unstable. In analogy with some tetraordinated, diamagnetic nickel mercaptides, which were known to be polymers, Jensen⁵¹ suggested that nickel (II) rubeanate must also be formulated by a polymeric structure VI in the form of a chain.

Ewens and Gibson⁵² have described a binuclear gold rubeanate, tetraethylidigold rubeanate, whose structure is represented by them by the configuration VII resembling

that of the nonelectrolyte (2-aminoethylthio) diethylgold studied by them. In this latter the sulphur atom has been found to display the reactivity typical of an organic sulphide. This illustrates the bridging capacity of the rubeanic acid molecule as well as its occurrence in the *trans* form in complex formation. The structure VII postulated by

Ewens and Gibson for metal rubeanates involves the formation of 5-membered rings and, for this reason, is preferable to that of Jensen with 4-membered rings which are not likely to contribute to the stability of the complex formed. The structures of copper (II), nickel (II), cobalt (II) and palladium (II) complexes of rubeanic acid are therefore best represented by a chain like polymeric structure VIII.

This assumption of the chain-like polymeric structure for the metal rubeanates has been strengthened by the work of Amon and Kane⁵⁵ who found that when a plastic sheet covered with the precipitate of metal rubeanic acid complex was stretched in one direction, the polymer chains were oriented parallel to each other; for, the polarisation of transmitted light could not be accounted for in any other way.

In the case of gold rubeanic acid complexes with gold in the trivalent state, an octahedral coordination for the metal atom should be assumed in order to satisfy its valency. This would necessitate the formation of a sheet like structure on polymerisation.

Recently Barcelo¹⁹ from a study of the infrared absorption bands of copper (II), nickel (II) and cobalt (II) rubeanates has suggested the structure IX for these compounds:

In this the rubeanic acid molecule is represented to react in its thionic form with the amido (-NH_2) group exercising the acid function, for which, however, there is little or no justification. Evidences furnished by the infrared spectra are also inadequate to warrant the above representation, as already stated in discussing the structure of rubeanic acid itself. The argument advanced in favour of this structure by Hurd *et al.*³⁶ that *NN'*-tetraethylrubeanic acid that contains no amido hydrogen does not react with Ni(II) ion in aqueous alcoholic solution carries little conviction. For, this only shows the absence of any hydrogen atom available for giving rise to the thio-enolic configuration responsible for complex formation.

It is curious to note that whereas nickel (II) rubeanate is diamagnetic like nickel II mercaptides, nickel (II) dimethylrubeanate has been found by Hurd *et al.*³⁶ to show paramagnetism with a moment value of 2.4 B.M. It seems not unlikely that the fairly drastic treatment to which it was subjected at a more or less elevated temperature during its purification produced a change in its structure from the square planar configuration to that of tetrahedral or octahedral type.

Uses

(a) *Detection of Metals.*—Rubeanic acid, and recently many of its derivatives, have been extensively investigated for use as an analytical reagent, particularly for the detection and determination of trace amounts of Cu, Ni, Co, Pd, Ru and Ag (cf. Wenger and Duckert—Editors, *Reagents for Qualitative Analysis*, Elsevier Publishing Co. Inc., New York, 1943; Welcher, *Organic Analytical Reagents* Vol. IV, Van Nostrand Co. Inc., New York, 1948).

First introduced by Ráy and Ray³ for the micro-detection of Cu, Ni and Co, the scope of applicability of rubeanic acid as a reagent in chemical analysis has widened considerably through the work of various investigators. Early studies were centred more or less on specifying the identification limits of individual metals and on interferences in their detection. The identification limits for the above mentioned metals by spot tests with rubeanic acid and some of its derivatives are given in Table 3 which also includes the limits by thread and capillary tests with the parent reagent.

A complete qualitative separation of a small amount of copper from a large amount of cadmium in presence of dilute sulphuric or acetic acid by rubeanic acid, using micro-chemical method, has been also reported by Ráy³.

Capillary separation of copper from nickel or cobalt on filter paper by means of rubeanic acid, which produces a central spot of olive-green copper rubeanate surrounded by a blue zone of nickel or a brown zone of cobalt precipitate, has been described by Feigl and

Kapulitzas⁴⁵. A disc chromatographic method of detecting all the three metals simultaneously has been developed by Pollard and McOmie⁵⁵. Rubenic acid is used here as a developer⁵⁶.

TABLE III

[R=Rubenic acid, DMR=Dimethylrubenic acid, DER=Diethylrubenic acid, DHxER=Di-(hydroxyethyl) rubenic acid, DIAR=Diisoamylrubenic acid, DBR=Dibenzylrubenic acid, DPhR=Diphenylrubenic acid].

Reagent	Identification limits (μg)					Reference
	Copper	Nickel	Cobalt	Palladium	Ruthenium	
R	0.012	0.006	0.030		0.20	3,32
	0.006	0.012	0.030			57
	0.002	0.0002	0.006			3 (thread test)
	0.002	0.006	0.002			3 (capillary test)
DMR	0.180	0.040	0.025	0.067		37
DER	"	"	"	"		37
DHxER	0.050	0.015	0.025	0.060		37
DIAR	0.050	0.020	0.030	0.100		37
DBR	0.100	0.040	0.035	0.060		37
DPhR	0.100	0.400	0.100	0.200	0.060	37

Using malonic acid and ethylenediamine as sequestering agent for interfering ions West⁵⁸ has utilized rubenic acid as a specific spot-test reagent for copper. The same author⁵⁹ has demonstrated a fascinating test in which 10^{-9} μg of copper can be detected by means of rubenic acid in human skin. The reagent has also been used for the detection of copper and nickel in steel^{59a}.

Thomson⁶⁰ has reported the detection of 0.002 μg of cobalt at a dilution of 1:1,000,000 by means of coloroscopic method.

Dubsky, Okac and Tritlek⁶¹ reported detection of bismuth with an acid solution of rubenic acid, which could not be confirmed⁶⁴.

Conditions for the detection of nickel on the surface of an ion-exchange resin with rubenic acid have been investigated by Fujimoto⁶². The sensitivity is 0.0021 μg of Ni at a limiting concentration of 1 in 1.9×10^7 .

(b) *Determination of Metals*.—Rubenic acid was first employed by Ray and Ray (loc. cit.) for the quantitative precipitation of copper, nickel and cobalt from ammoniacal solution. Since then it has been studied by several investigators for use as a colorimetric reagent for the determination of a number of transition metals, primarily of copper. Recently attention has been directed to some of its derivatives also, which have proved to be quite useful for the purpose and even to possess special advantages in some cases.

Using protective colloids such as gelatine or gum acacia copper has been determined colorimetrically from the measurement of the intensity of its greenish black colour^{63,64,65}. A buffer solution of ammonium acetate + acetic acid or malonic acid ($\text{pH}=4$) has also been employed for the purpose in place of a protective colloid⁶⁵. Copper has been determined

by these means in steel, alloys and other products by various workers⁶⁶. Measurements were made spectrophotometrically by some of the later workers. Tartrate, citrate and malonic acid were used to sequester interfering ions.

Jacobs and Yoe^{40,44,67} used 8 different derivatives of rubeanic acid besides rubeanic acid itself for the spectrophotometric determination of copper using gum acacia as the protective colloid. Xavier and Rây³⁷ employed *NN'*-di-(2-hydroxyethyl) rubeanic acid and *NN'*-diphenylrubeanic acid in acetone-pyridine and aqueous pyridine solution respectively for the same purpose, as copper complexes of these two derivatives were found to be fairly soluble in pyridine. With *NN'*-diphenylrubeanic acid copper was determined in aqueous pyridine in this manner in presence of several interfering ions like Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , Sn^{2+} , MoO_4^{2-} , and WO_4^{2-} using disodium versenate (ethylenediaminetetraacetate) as a masking agent. In the case of *NN'*-di-(2-hydroxyethyl) rubeanic acid the colour of the copper complex in pyridine was also partially masked. Table IV gives the wave lengths of absorbance maximum, molar extinction coefficients and sensitivities of the coloured copper complexes studied. It would appear from this table that the values of sensitivity and molar extinction coefficient are much higher with protective colloids than in pyridine solution. But it might be pointed out that the coloured complex of copper (II) *NN'*-di-(2-hydroxyethyl) rubeanic acid and of copper (II) *NN'*-diphenylrubeanic acid can be extracted out from their pyridine solutions by butyl¹ or amyl¹ alcohol, whereby the method of estimation might be further refined and made more sensitive.

TABLE IV

Copper (II) complexes

NN'-bis or di-(carboxymethyl) rubeanic acid, $\text{HOOCH}_2\text{NHSCCSNHCH}_2\text{COOH}=\text{DCxMR}$; *NN'*-bis-(2-sulphoethyl) rubeanic acid, disodium salt, $\text{NaSO}_3\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NHSCCSNHCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{SO}_3\text{Na}=\text{DSER}$; *NN'*-bis-(3dimethylaminopropyl) rubeanic acid, $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{NCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NHSCCSNHCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2=\text{dDMAPR}$.; *NN'*-bis-(3-methoxypropyl) rubeanic acid, $\text{CH}_3\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{NHSCCSNH}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{OCH}_3=\text{DMxPR}$; *NN'*-Dicyclohexylrubeanic acid, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{NHSCCSNH}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11})_2=\text{DcHR}$; *NN'*-didodecylrubeanic acid, $\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{11}\text{NHSCCSNH}(\text{CH}_2)_{11}\text{CH}_3=\text{DdDR}$; other symbols have the same significance as in Table III.

Reagent	λ_{max}	Mol. extinc. coeff.	Sensitivity (l/cm^2)	Reference
R	385 m μ	15,800	0.0037 (Sandell) 0.0190 (practical)	40, 67
DER	365	12,900	0.0050(S)	40, 67
DCxMR	340	6,030	0.0150(S)	40, 67.
DHxER	380	15,600	0.0040(S)	40, 67
DHxER in pyridine soln.	390 (measured at)	8,800	0.0070(S) 0.0300(p)	37
D $\overline{\text{S}}\text{ER}$	380	12,900	0.0050(S)	40, 67
dDMAPR	365	15,000	0.0040(S)	40, 67
DMxPR	380	15,700	0.0040(S)	40, 67
DcHR	385	10,400	0.0060(S)	40, 67
DdDR	385	26,700	0.0020(S)	40, 67
DPhR (pyridine soln.)	420	6,060	0.0100(S) 0.0800(P)	37

Amperometric and complexometric titration methods for estimating copper by rubeanic acid have also been reported by some authors⁶⁸.

Nickel and cobalt have also been determined spectrophotometrically by Jacobs and Yoe⁴⁹ as well as by Xavier and Ray³⁷ using rubeanic acid and a number of its *NN'*-disubstituted derivatives. The first named authors employed gum acacia to maintain the coloured complexes in solution and the latter used the alcoholic or aqueous pyridine solution. The values of $\lambda_{\max}$, molar extinction coefficient (ϵ) and sensitivity in γ/cm^2 for the coloured species are listed in Table V.

TABLE V

Cobalt and nickel complexes

[Symbols for the reagents have the same significance as in Table IV]

Reagent	C o b a l t			N i c k e l			Reference
	$\lambda_{\max}$.	ϵ	Sensitivity	$\lambda_{\max}$.	ϵ	Sensitivity	
R	370	13,000	0.0040(S) 0.0200(p)	640	8,930	0.0070(S) 0.0340(p)	40
	400	13,800	0.0040(S) 0.0100(p)	530	5,900	0.0100(S) 0.0400(p)	37
DMR	395	14,600	0.0040(S) 0.0250(p)	485	7,900	0.0075(S) 0.0300(p)	37
DER	395	14,200	0.0045(S) 0.0300(p)	490	7,500	0.0080(S) 0.0300(p)	37
	350	13,600	0.0040(S)	510	5,570	0.0110(S)	40
DiAR	390	10,600	0.0056(S) 0.0300(p)	510	8,170	0.0070(S) 0.0300(p)	37
DHxER	400	10,000	0.0060(S)	490	4,980	0.0180(S)	40
DCxMR	400	12,700	0.0050(S)	345	6,900	0.0090(S)	40
DSEr	345	5,900	0.0100(S)	510	4,100	0.0140(S)	40
dDMAPR	350	14,800	0.0040(S) 0.0250(p)	500	7,150	0.0080(S) 0.0390(p)	40
DMxPR	345	18,500	0.0030(S)	510	6,150	0.0090(S)	40
DcHR	380	8,800	0.0070(S)	520	5,900	0.0100(S)	40
DdDR	400	16,800	0.0040(S)	525	11,400	0.0070(S)	40
DPhR	410	18,300	0.0030(S) 0.0250(p)	510	8,000	0.0075(S) 0.0300(p)	37

S—Sandell, p=practical.

The spectrophotometric determination of cobalt in pyridine solution can be carried out in the presence of a moderate amount of nickel (using KCN as the masking agent),

copper and silver (using thiourea) and of iron (III) using fluoride. Interference by copper in moderate amount is also eliminated by the addition of KCN^{37,40}.

Jacobs and Yoe⁴⁰ have described a method for the simultaneous spectrophotometric determination of cobalt, nickel and copper in the same solution (using) rubeanic acid and *NN'*-bis-(3-dimethylaminopropyl) rubeanic acid in presence of gum acacia. The method is based on the use of the values of extinction coefficients of the coloured complexes of the three metals at the optimum wave lengths of their absorbance for deriving equations for the determination of one or more components. Results of analysis of several synthetic and standard samples by this method have also been reported by the authors.

Palladium is precipitated quantitatively by rubeanic acid at pH 3⁶⁹. The precipitate is soluble in pyridine giving an intense orange-yellow solution. The metal has been estimated spectrophotometrically by rubeanic acid in alcoholic pyridine medium. By the addition of sodium versenate followed by the extraction of the coloured species by isoamyl alcohol interference due to Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Cd(II), Fe(III), etc. can be eliminated, but Pt(IV), Au (III) and Ag (I) would interfere³⁷. Xavier and Rây³⁷ have also employed dimethyl, diethyl and diphenylrubeanic acids for the estimation of palladium by spectrophotometric method in alcoholic or aqueous pyridine medium. With bis-(2-hydroxyethyl) and diisoamylrubeanic acids, however, pyridine was found to be unsuitable, as the colour did not fully develop in alkaline medium. In their case palladium was estimated in alcoholic solution³⁷.

The values for the wave length of absorbance maximum or optimum absorbance, the molar extinction coefficient and the sensitivity of coloured palladium complexes of rubeanic acid and some of its derivatives are recorded in Table VI.

The blue colour developed by ruthenium in strong hydrochloric acid solution with rubeanic acid and its derivatives has been utilized for its determination by spectrophotometric measurement^{69a,37}. Rubeanic acid and its dimethyl, diethyl and bis-(2-hydroxyethyl) derivatives all give maximum absorbance in the region of 610-670 m μ . They all show practically the same sensitivity of 0.01 γ cm² (S) and 0.04 γ /cm² (p) with a molar extinction coefficient of 5,200 for rubeanic and bis-(2-hydroxyethyl)rubeanic acids, and of 5,800 for dimethyl and diethylrubeanic acids. Osmium has been found to interfere in the determination.

TABLE VI
Palladium complexes.

Reagent.	$\lambda_{\max}$.	Molar extinc. coeff.	Sensitivity (T/cm^2)
Rubeanic acid (Rba)	410	4,600	0.0130 (Sandell) 0.0500 (practical)
Dimethyl-Rba	395 (op.)	4,080	0.0140 (S) 0.0500 (p)
Diethyl-Rba	395	4,680	0.0140 (S) 0.0500 (p)
Bis-(2-hydroxyethyl)-Rba	390	5,520	0.0110 (S) 0.0500 (p)
Diisoamyl-Rba	395	5,790	0.0110 (S) 0.0400 (p)
Diphenyl-Rba	395	7,920	0.0075 (S) 0.0250 (p)

Silver has been determined spectrophotometrically from the yellowish brown colour which it develops by treatment with rubeanic acid in aqueous solution³⁷. Measurements were made at 390 m μ at pH 4.0-4.6. It gives a practical sensitivity value of 0.05 γ Ag/cm².

A comparison of the wave lengths of maximum absorbance and sensitivity values of coloured complexes of the metals with rubeanic acid and its various derivatives shows that no significant chromotropic effect is obtained by mono-substitution of alkyl or aryl groups at the two ends of the parent ligand, except an appreciable shift in the case of the nickel complex from 460 m μ to 500 m μ region and even to about 350 m μ for the nickel complex of *NN'*-bis-(carboxymethyl) rubeanic acid. There is also no marked difference in sensitivity observed as the result of substitution.

From the spectrophotometric measurement at 625 m μ of the absorbance of light reflected by the blue-violet spot of nickel (II) rubeanate on a filter paper a method for the microchemical determination of nickel in quantitative chromatography has been described by Vaeck⁷⁰.

A turbidimetric titration method for cobalt by rubeanic acid in solution containing gum acacia has been developed by Tananaev and Shapiro⁷¹. Incidentally the authors have confirmed the composition of cobaltic rubeanate as $\text{Co}_2(\text{C}_4\text{S}_2\text{N}_2\text{H}_2)_2$.

(c) *Miscellaneous Applications*.—A number of new and quite interesting applications of rubeanic acid and its derivatives in the field of arts and industries has been suggested particularly in recent times. This has widened the scope of investigation on this remarkable reagent and its derivatives, whose number is increasing rapidly with time.

An application of rubeanic acid was suggested somewhat earlier by Nilsson⁷² for toning or intensifying photographic images.

The antibacterial action of rubeanic acid and its effectiveness, when present in very low concentration of 10 mg per cent, against certain organisms like staphylococci has been recently investigated⁷³. Several *NN'*-disubstituted rubeanic acids have been found similarly effective in inhibiting staphylococci, *E. coli*, pleuropneumonia-like organisms and tuberculi bacilli⁷⁴.

Rubeanic acid and many of its disubstituted derivatives have been found effective as metal deactivators in petroleum products, when employed in concentration of 0.001 to 1% by weight⁷⁵.

The autoxidation of cyclohexane catalysed by the presence of copper (II) is retarded by the use of *NN'*-dicyclohexylrubeanic acid which masks the activity of copper⁷⁶.

Rubeanic acid has been found to be quite effective in removing copper (II) turbidity from wine and is preferable to potassium ferrocyanide which is commonly used for the purpose⁷⁷.

Metal complexes of rubeanic acid and its derivatives have been suggested for use as pigments.

Mixed with a fusible metal soap, rubeanic acid and its derivatives have been employed in thermal duplicating processes⁷⁸. The usefulness of these reagents in electrochemical reproduction has also been suggested (Mallinckrodt, loc. cit.)

Some *NN'*-disubstituted rubeanic acids have been found useful as vulcanization accelerators⁷⁹.

NN'-Dibutylrubeanic acid has been found to produce complete defoliation of mature

cotton⁸⁰. Rubeanic acid and many of its disubstituted aliphatic derivatives have been found to inhibit the germination of some grass seeds, and to retard the growth of various seeds and grasses¹⁴.

Rubeanic acid and many of its derivatives have been found useful as rodent repellent while *NN'*-didodecylrubeanic acid has been reported to possess activity as a bird repellent⁸¹.

Rubeanic acid and its derivatives have been used in organic preparations for the synthesis of a wide variety of heterocyclic compounds.

It is hoped that this review will be found helpful to those who are interested in this new series of reagents which hold promise of such a wide variety of applications.

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